

INTEGRATIVE MODEL OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT FOR FUTURE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

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In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the integration of information technology (IT) has become a cornerstone for fostering innovation and preparing future generations for the dynamic demands of the digital era. As educational paradigms shift towards a more technology-centric approach, the role of information technology teachers has gained unprecedented significance. These educators are tasked with not only imparting technical knowledge but also cultivating a diverse set of competencies essential for navigating the complexities of contemporary educational environments.

This delves into the intricate process of developing professional competence among future information technology teachers within the context of innovative education. The traditional approaches to teacher training often fall short in addressing the multifaceted nature of IT education, necessitating a comprehensive and integrative model that considers the dynamic interplay between pedagogical strategies, technological advancements, and the evolving needs of learners

Our exploration seeks to establish a theoretical framework that synthesizes various dimensions of professional competence development. By integrating elements such as pedagogical acumen, technological proficiency, adaptability to change, and a keen understanding of the socio-cultural aspects of learning, this model aims to provide a roadmap for cultivating well-rounded information technology teachers capable of navigating the challenges of modern education.

The interdisciplinary nature of this investigation draws on insights from educational psychology, instructional design, and information technology, among other fields, to create a synthesis that goes beyond the conventional silos of teacher training. As we embark on this journey, the article endeavors to contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective teacher preparation, with a focus on the specialized needs of information technology educators in the 21st century.

In the subsequent sections, we will delve into the key components of our proposed integrative model, highlighting the interconnectedness of various competencies and their collective impact on the professional development of future information technology teachers. Through this exploration, we aspire to provide educators, policymakers, and researchers with valuable insights that can inform the design and implementation of innovative teacher training programs tailored to the demands of the digital age.

The landscape of contemporary education is inextricably linked to the rapid advancements in information technology, necessitating a paradigm shift in teacher preparation programs. As educators grapple with the dynamic challenges posed by the digital age, a growing body of literature underscores the critical importance of cultivating professional competence among future information technology teachers. This literature review synthesizes key findings from existing studies, shedding light on the multifaceted dimensions of teacher preparation within the context of innovative education.

1. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK):

At the intersection of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge lies the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). This conceptual model emphasizes the need for teachers to integrate these three domains seamlessly. In the context of information technology education, TPACK provides a foundational understanding, but the evolving landscape requires a more expansive model that accounts for socio-cultural, psychological, and adaptive dimensions.

2. Adaptability and Continuous Learning:

The dynamic nature of information technology necessitates teachers who are not only adept in current technologies but also possess the ability to adapt to emerging trends. Research by Fullan (2013) and Darling-Hammond (2017) underscores the significance of fostering a culture of continuous learning among educators, highlighting the need for teacher preparation programs to instill adaptive expertise.

3. Socio-Cultural Context of Learning:

The role of socio-cultural factors in education is well-established (Vygotsky, 1978). In the context of information technology, understanding the socio-cultural dynamics of diverse learner populations becomes paramount. Research by Mishra and Yadav (2016) stresses the importance of considering cultural contexts in technology integration, emphasizing the need for teachers to navigate the socio-cultural dimensions of their classrooms.

4. Innovative Pedagogies and Active Learning:

The efficacy of innovative pedagogies in information technology education has been extensively explored. The works of Hattie (2009) and Puentedura (2006) emphasize the impact of active learning strategies and transformative pedagogies in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. Integrating these pedagogical approaches into teacher preparation becomes imperative for future educators.

5. Collaborative Learning Communities:

The collaborative nature of information technology demands that teachers work effectively within interdisciplinary teams. Wenger's (1998) communities of practice framework highlights the importance of collaborative learning environments for professional development. This literature underscores the necessity for teacher training programs to foster collaborative skills and build communities of practice among future information technology educators.

In synthesizing these strands of literature, it becomes evident that an integrative model of professional competence development for future information technology teachers must transcend conventional boundaries. By drawing on the strengths of existing frameworks while addressing their limitations, the proposed model seeks to offer a comprehensive and nuanced approach to teacher preparation in the context of innovative education. The subsequent sections of this article will expound upon the intricacies of this integrative model, providing a theoretical foundation for its application in shaping the next generation of information technology educators.

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